

Ongoing histochemical assay of reproductive organs of plants transformed with the pΔGus1177 plasmid permitted detection of GUS activity in the sterile lemmas and in the lemma and palea of the spikelets and in the maternal tissues of young developing anthers containing uninucleated microspores, but not in ovaries or in the walls of mature anthers containing binucleated pollen. We also found activity in pollen and in the pericarp of the mature seed.

Tissue specificity and developmental regulation of the rice *ltp* promoter make it a good candidate for driving genes conferring resistance to leaf-felder and blast that mainly develops on young leaves.

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Pest resistance—diseases

Sources of resistance to sheath blight

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Sheath blight of rice, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, is becoming a major rice disease because of the increased use of nitrogen fertilizer and shorter, high-tillering cultivars, which together produce a microclimate that enhances disease incidence.

Because chemical control is costly and not effective, we screened breeding lines developed at ARI to identify resistant sources. This experiment was conducted with 166, 147, and 144 entries during the 1993, 1994, and 1995 wet

Table 1. Frequency distribution of sheath blight disease among entries. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India. 1993-95.

Disease scale	Entries (no.)		
	1993	1994	1995
0	0	1	0
1	3	0	1
2	4	1	1
3	9	0	0
4	5	2	0
5	11	5	1
6	6	1	6
7	71	12	16
8	39	39	40
9	19	86	80

Table 2. Reaction to sheath blight disease of promising lines and other characters. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India. 1993-95.

Line	Parentage	Disease score ^a			Mean	Plant height (cm)	Tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
		1993	1994	1995				
RNR15336	Saleem/W12708	1.8	0.0	0.6	0.8	89	9.0	5.7
RNR82096	Tellahamsa/Akaswari	0.6	1.6	1.2	1.1	89	8.4	5.5
TN1 (check)		6.2	8.6	7.8	7.5	91	10.2	4.2

^a Mean of 10 hills.

seasons, respectively, under irrigated transplanted conditions. TN1 was the susceptible check. Each entry was grown in two 2-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Artificial inoculation was done at maximum tillering by placing 2-3 typha bits containing the inoculum in the middle of the hill just above the water level, tied with a rubber band. Ten hills were inoculated per entry.

To compute relative lesion height, the average vertical height of the upper most lesion and average plant height were measured at grain filling. Results revealed that most of the entries were highly susceptible (Table 1) but two entries, RNR15336 and RNR82096, produced low relative lesion height (Table 2) and appear to be resistant to sheath blight.

RNR15336 (120 d duration) and RNR82096 (140 d duration) have long slender grains and are being evaluated in advanced yield trials. ■

Effect of blast disease on rice yield

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We studied the effect of blast disease on 12 rice varieties and lines at Edirne and Uzunköprü, Turkey, in 1995. Eighty kilometers separate the two sites.

The experiment was laid out at both sites in a randomized complete block design with four replications under continuous irrigation. Plot size was 20 m². Four hundred and fifty pre-germinated seeds m⁻² were broadcast in standing water on 20 May.

The same agronomic techniques were practiced at both sites. Fertilizer was applied at 150 kg N ha⁻¹ in three equal splits (basal dressing and top-dressing at tiller initiation and panicle initiation) and 80 kg P ha⁻¹ as a single basal dressing.